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Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable “D 4.2: Taxonomy of governance frameworks in Europe, learnings from the St-Vincent-de-Paul project and consolidated recommendations for the P2Green governance framework” is the second of two deliverables produced in the frame of Task 4.1: Review and benchmark of existing governance frameworks in Europe. Task 4.1 is part of Work Package 4, ‘Building the governance framework’.

Deliverable D4.2 is divided into two different but complementary parts.

Part A “Final study and consolidated recommendations from the case of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (Paris, France)” is an analysis of the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul project in Paris.

The City of Paris approved an innovative project in 2020 to implement a separate urine management system in the future Saint-Vincent-de-Paul district, which will be progressively delivered from 2026 to 2029. This project, featuring 600 housing units and various amenities, is ground-breaking in the Île-de-France region and France, representing a unique initiative in large urban centres in Europe. Urine collected from the district will be processed on-site into fertiliser for use in Parisian plantations. The governance of this project is noteworthy, with the City of Paris taking the lead while collaborating with numerous public and private stakeholders across different phases of the project (design, construction, operation).

Part A contains an analysis of the decision-making process and stakeholder dynamics during the project's design phase (2018-2020) and the early stages of its construction phase (2021-2025) at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul. Drawing from this analysis, the report offers governance recommendations and identifies barriers and drivers to promote the success of similar projects across Europe.

Part B contains the “Analysis and provisional recommendations of case studies” which is the second part of a benchmark of governance frameworks adopted in existing European projects related to circular N & P solutions.

In deliverable D4.1, the first part of the benchmark, the focus was on the identification and first analysis of a total of eight projects. A first broad search for projects resulted in a list of 55 projects that were examined with the focus to identify practical, and if possible mature examples of projects. This resulted in the choice of the 8 presented projects, additionally. In D4.2 four further projects are were analysed, and additionally all 12 projects are presented in a comparison.

As P2Green lies in between different policy fields and competences: wastewater management, spatial planning and construction, agriculture, green spaces management, it also cuts across jurisdiction as well as fostering rural-urban linkages. For this reason, it is not possible to find relevant examples in the sense of a one-size-fits-all approach. Therefore, the deliverable Part B rather aims at identifying examples that reflect the

diversity of situations and governance arrangements in P2Green's work on circular N & P solutions.

Where possible, the analysis of the cases also considers different phases of projects, and that the actors involved and the governance structures of projects also change according to the phase of a project (strong political involvement in early phases, and then practitioners).

After the analysis of the four cases, a taxonomy of governance frameworks and policy instruments from the 12 cases is presented.

Part A: Final study and consolidated recommendations from the case of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (Paris, France)

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Part A : Final study and consolidated recommendations from the case of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (Paris, France)

Summary

The City of Paris validated in 2020 the innovative project aimed at experimenting with separate urine management in the future district of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul, located in the 14th arrondissement of Paris. Under construction since 2021, the district, which will include 600 housing units and different amenities, will be delivered gradually, over 2026-2029. Urine collected at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul will be treated and transformed in fertiliser on site, and the fertiliser will be used on plantations by the City of Paris.

This is the first time that such a project has seen the light in the Île-de-France region and in France. More broadly, there is currently no other separate urine management project in city centre of large urban areas on this scale in Europe. Hence the interest in devoting a study to the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul case, in order to analyse the dynamics of implementation of the project and to draw lessons and recommendations for other actors who would like to experiment excreta source separation.

In terms of governance, this project has the particularity of being piloted by the City of Paris, while involving numerous other public and private actors, with new stakeholders at each phase of the project (design/construction/operation).

This final report, delivered at M36, describes and analyses the decision-making process and the stakeholders' dynamics linked to the urine separate management project at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul during its design phase (2018-2020) and during the first years of its construction phase (2021-2025).

Based on the analysis of the case of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul, the report formulates recommendations in terms of governance framework to build, and points out barriers to tackle and drivers to mobilize, in order to encourage the development and success of other excreta source separation projects in Europe

1. Introduction

1.1 Context and interest of the case of Saint Vincent-de-Paul

Since the 2010s, an emerging dynamic in favour of excreta separate collection and valorisation has been observed in France, notably in Paris and in the Île-de-France region, with the launch of a first research program on the thematic in 2015 (the OCAPi program²: <https://www.leesu.fr/ocapi/>), and then with the emergence of first urban collective projects³. Among these projects, the most important, led by the City of Paris, takes place in the urban development zone of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (SVDP) in the 14th arrondissement of Paris. The future district of SVDP (in construction since 2021, with a progressive delivery over 2026-2029) is intended to be a pilot site for ecological transition policies of the City of Paris. The municipality and its public developer Paris & Métropole Aménagement (P&MA), validated at the end of 2020 the project aimed at experimenting with separate urine management (SUM) on the scale of the entire district, which will include 600 housing units, as well as businesses and facilities (including a nursery, a school and a gymnasium). Urine will be treated and transformed in fertiliser on site, in a local plant at SVDP, and the fertiliser will be used on plantations (and maybe lawns) by the City of Paris.

This is the first time that such a project has seen the light in the Île-de-France region and in France. More broadly, there is currently no other SUM project in the city centre of large urban areas on this scale in Europe. Hence the interest in devoting a study to the SVDP case, in order to analyse the dynamics of genesis and implementation of the project. In terms of governance, the size of the project (entire district) leads to the involvement of multiple stakeholders. A particularity is the strong involvement of the City of Paris: at the origin of the SUM project, it is also the city which will manage the exploitation of the urine collection and recovery system, even if it will also integrate private actors.

This report describes and analyses the decision-making process and the stakeholders' dynamics linked to the SUM project implementation at SVDP. We seek to learn lessons and to formulate recommendations from this case in terms of a governance framework to

² Attached to Water, Environment and Urban Systems Laboratory (LEESU) at the École des Ponts ParisTech and to the CEREMA (which stands for Centre for Studies and Expertise on Risks, the Environment, Mobility and Urban Planning).

³ Concerning the City of Paris, particularly involved on the subject of excreta source separation for several years, it has, beyond the SVDP project, installed dry toilets in the *Jeanne d'Arc school* (Paris 13th) in 2022 and plans to also do it in its *Climate Academy* (Paris 4th). Among other initiatives in the region of Île-de-France, we can quote: the equipment of the *French headquarter of the European Spatial Agency* in Paris 15th in urine diversion flush toilets, with a nitrification-distillation unit on site in order to produce fertiliser (in service since 2023) ; of the *Jacques Chirac leisure center* in the City of Rosny-sous-Bois (department of Seine-Saint-Denis) and of the *restaurant Le 211* in Paris 19th in dry toilets (in service since 2020 and 2021). The *Lot C15B* (office building with university restaurant) in Palaiseau (Essonne), is also equipped since 2023 with urine diversion flush toilets and a local treatment device producing a fertiliser which will be used on neighboring agricultural lands.

build, and in terms of barriers to tackle and drivers to mobilize, in order to encourage the development and success of other source separation projects in Europe, which is one of the objectives of the P2Green project.

1.2 Structure of Part A

The report is structured as follows:

Part 2 presents the methodological approach;

Part 3 analyses the interactions of stakeholders, the socio-technical choices made, the dynamics of implementation of the separate urine management project at the SVDP, the issues encountered and the way in which they are taken into account;

Part 4 presents the results of a survey of a panel of future residents at SVDP, as well as challenges and actions linked to adapting users' practices to toilets;

Part 5 highlights lessons and recommendations from the SVDP case on governance frameworks and on barriers and drivers for source separation projects.

2. Methodological approach

Since March 2023, Aurélie Joveniaux has been carrying out as research officer at the City of Paris a work aimed to analyse the separate urine management (SUM) project at Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (SVDP), which is currently in its construction phase (since 2021, see Figure 2 p.17).

The analysis presented in this report is based on the material collected during a series of semi-structured interviews (26) carried out with Bernard de Gouvello (CEREMA/OCAPI program) with different actors involved in the project studied: agents of the City of Paris and of P&MA, members of the project management assistance group to P&MA for SUM at SVDP, of the company which built the urine collection network, of social housing companies, etc. (Table 1). Grey literature related to the project and produced by the City of Paris and P&MA was also consulted.

Table 1 Type of actors interviewed

Type of actors and structures	Number of interviews
Agents of different departments of the City of Paris	6
Agents of the public developer Paris Métropole Aménagement (P&MA)	5
Member of the project management assistance group to P&MA	3
Employees of Paris Habitat (social housing company)	3
Employee of Artelia company, prime contractor for public spaces at SVDP	1
Employee of Colas company, which built the urine collection network	1
Employee of a company producing and selling urine-based fertiliser	1
Future residents of SVDP	6

Moreover, fieldwork led to participation in five monitoring committees organized by P&MA on the SUM project over 2023-2025, as well as in the first committee of European experts on the project which was held on June 30, 2025.

This report also draws in part on the results of research work previously carried out over the period 2019-2021 as part of the DESIGN project (<https://design.cnrs.fr/>), funded by the French National Research Agency and in which Aurélie Joveniaux and Bernard de Gouvello participated as members of the OCAPI team. A study on the SUM project at

SVDP during its design phase (2018-2020) was led and resulted in a report (Joveniaux and de Gouvello, 2021).

Finally, this report feeds on the results of a survey conducted in 2024 on a panel of future residents of SVDP. This survey was carried out as part of a partnership involving the City of Paris and the Ocapa research team (ENPC/CEREMA), funded by the Agence de l'Eau Seine-Normandie (AESN). A report presenting the results of this survey was published (Joveniaux and de Gouvello, 2024). The results of this survey are proving useful in the context of reflection on the governance aspects of SUM projects, hence we present a summary of its results here.

3. Stakeholders’ interactions, implementation dynamics and issues encountered in the separate urine management project

Table gives an overview on the SVDP project, it presents the different steps along the cycle and the categories and sectors of policy making linked to them. It further shows institutional, regulatory and economic framework and instruments.

Table 2 SVDP project overview table

The Goal	Implementation of waste water separation, waste water treatment plant and production of N&P fertiliser at the SVDP-development project		
Steps	Collection	Logistics and treatment	Fertiliser use
Description	Separate collection of urine: 600 housing units + various amenities	Public urine network (gravity supported by vacuum) + public urine treatment plant at SVDP - nitrification-distillation	Production of a fertiliser AURIN®
Categories/ sectors of policy making	<p>Encourage resource-oriented sanitation in the build environment or temporary sanitation</p> <p>Local/regional - Protection of water and aquatic ecosystems; "scissor effect" Seine + production/use of a natural and renewable fertilizer - Possibility of reversibility of the system in case of problem</p> <p>National/international - Environmental and food safety issues (context of tensions on fertilizers with Ukraine war) - Adaptation to climate change and demographic evolution</p>	<p>(Non-) Public authorities of the resource-oriented WW-Management system</p> <p>City of Paris owner and pilot of the management of network and plant at SVDP (incl. probably a delegation to a private company) - Main departments involved in the City: "Direction de la Propreté et de l'eau" (DPE) for the operation of network and plant, "Direction des Espaces Verts et de l'Environnement" (DEVE) for the utilization of fertilizer</p> <p>Involvement of public authorities that enabled wastewater management system Governance issues: actors' alignment in the City (different departments involved) and with other structures and stakeholders implied</p>	<p>Drivers and brakes for promotion of urino-fertilizer</p> <p>Utilization of the fertilizer on plantations at the Rungis Horticultural Center by DEVE Operating costs +-0 due to utilization of fertilizer Missing market authorisation for AURIN®</p>
	<p>Institutional, regulatory and economic framework and instruments</p> <p>Mobilize: political support of elected officials from the City of Paris Incentive: subsidies of AESN (up to 80% for public investments and to 40% for private investments) Research: support from the OCAPI team</p> <p>Regulation: obligation to connect to public sewer in collective sanitation areas</p> <p>Regulate: Marketing authorisation for AURIN® missing in France Incentive: independence of fossil N&P and food safety issues</p>		
Target audience	<p>Local -> collection, treatment and valorisation on local level includes city planning, accomodation, sanitation, green spaces and agriculture</p> <p>Regional -> stricter regulations for pollution of aquatic environments</p> <p>National -> National strategies</p> <p>EU -> EU environmental strategies for strikter regulations within the N&P cycle</p>		

3.1 Context of genesis of this innovative project: a political order

In 2016, an urban development zone was created on the site of the former SVDP hospital in the 14th arrondissement in Paris. This 3.4 ha (8.4 acre) site is the target of a conversion project to develop an eco-neighbourhood with 600 housing units, businesses and various facilities: nursery, school, gymnasium, cinema, etc. (see Figure 1). Construction began in 2021 and should be completed in 2029. The City of Paris wants to make SVDP a pilot site for its ecological transition policies. The separate urine management (SUM) project in SVDP was driven by elected municipal officials, who asked in 2018 to study the possibility of trialing this innovative approach in the future eco-neighbourhood.

Figure 1 The SVDP development project

Two elected officials of the City of Paris (Mao Peninou and Jean-Louis Missika, sanitation and planning deputies) are behind the project. In 2015-2016, they were made aware of the theme of urine source separation and the associated issues (preservation of aquatic environments and use of urine as fertiliser) by a researcher from the OCAPI team, Fabien Esculier (Esculier, 2018; Esculier *et al.*, 2018). They then looked for an urban development operation where they could experiment with such a device.

The SVDP operation appeared to these elected officials as a favourable context for it. It is indeed an operation which aims for environmental excellence, the development of the circular economy and the experimentation of new urban practices. The creation of an innovative separate sanitation system based on urine collection could be part of these objectives. Furthermore, in terms of schedule, the SVDP district's project was still in its early stages and it was therefore possible to consider integrating such a system. At the

beginning of 2018, the deputy mayor Jean-Louis Missika asked the public developer P&MA, in charge of the development of the district, to study the possibility to integrate SUM in the SVDP project.

3.2 SUM project which had to fit into the schedule of the district development project

Figure 2 p.17 presents in parallel the schedule of the district development project and that of the SUM project at SVDP, as well as the interferences between the two.

The design phase of the SVDP district project took place over the period 2016-2020 and that of the SUM project over the period 2018-2020. Deconstruction works on some buildings took place over 2018-2020. Construction works on the district began in 2021; the same goes for the SUM system. It is planned that the SVDP district will be progressively delivered between 2026 and 2029 (depending on the lots and buildings).

Unlike other innovations (such as the “zero discharge” objective for rainwater for example), SUM was not planned in the initial project of the SVDP district. This perspective, integrated in 2018 into the SVDP project, had thus to be studied and discussed, and then adopted and clarified gradually, in a dialectic process as the district project progressed.

In June 2018, during the first phase of consultation with groups of architects and developers for the 10 lots to be built in the neighbourhood, SUM was not yet mentioned in the requirements to be taken into account. In March 2019, the groups which applied to develop the 10 lots were asked to include the possibility of SUM in their projects⁴, even if the option was still under study and without certainty of implementation.

⁴ To this end, they were asked to set aside spaces and passages in the buildings so that the project could be implemented if approved.

Figure 2 Chronology of the district development project and of the SUM project

In June 2018, a first feasibility study concerning SUM at SVDP was ordered by the developer P&MA from the company Evoloop, specialized in *in situ* recycling systems. The feasibility study, carried out during the summer of 2018, considered three urine collection scenarios on a more or less large scale (from a single building to all SVDP lots). The study highlighted the fact that investment costs would be more easily amortized in a large-scale scenario. The results of this study were presented in October 2018 by P&MA to the SVDP steering committee, bringing together elected officials and managers of the various services involved in the City of Paris. The steering committee paid attention to the subject at the end of 2018, and stressed on the need to explore it further.

In June 2019, P&MA launched a call for tenders for a project management assistance mission for SUM at SVDP. A new study was conducted in 2019-2020. The SUM project has been validated at the end of 2020 (see below). Note that a decision had to be made on this date, so that the SUM project could be integrated in time into the district development project. The experiment is indeed part of a larger urban development project, which imposes its schedule for the decision-making process.

3.3 Design and decision-making process: stakeholders involved and actors' alignment issues

Figure 3 presents the system of stakeholders involved in the design phase of the SUM project at SVDP.

Figure 3 . System of stakeholders involved in the design phase (2018-2020)

Author: Aurélie Joveniaux, City of Paris & Ecole des Ponts ParisTech, 2024.

The developer of the future SVP district, on behalf of the City of Paris, is the public establishment **Paris & Métropole Aménagement (P&MA)**. P&MA is in charge of the development of the entire district, and therefore of the design of the urine collection and recovery system. In June 2019, P&MA submitted a call for tenders for a project management assistance mission aimed at assisting it in “the definition and operational monitoring of a separate urine management strategy within the SVDP district”.

In September 2019, a **project management assistance group** was selected bringing together four companies with varied skills: Tilia, a company which supports public and private actors in the technical assembly of projects linked to energy, water and sanitation; Symchowicz & Weissberg, a law firm specializing in public and private business law; Evoloop, a company specialized in circular economy; Louise Raguét, an independent designer specialized in ecological sanitation and support for users on the subject.

The **City of Paris**, which is at the initiative of the SUM project at SVDP, will own the public urine collection network, as well as the treatment plant. It is the City which will pilot the operation of the system, even if it would be probably with the help of private companies (cf. 3.6). The design of the SUM project was the subject of joint work between P&MA and the City of Paris, with constant back and forth between the two structures.

The SUM system at SVDP is an innovative project, which involves a change in practices, new skills, and which raises the question of the sharing of roles and responsibilities between the different actors involved. One of the main challenges during the design phase of the project was to succeed in involving and aligning the operational actors from the different Departments concerned within the City of Paris, in particular the « **Direction de la Propreté et de l’Eau** » (**DPE, Waste Management and Water Department**) and the « **Direction des Espaces Verts et de l’Environnement** » (**DEVE, Green Spaces and Environment Department**). The agents of these Departments indeed initially reacted to the SUM project with some reservations. Technical, logistical, but also financial questions were raised by DPE and DEVE agents: who is responsible and who finances? DEVE’s acceptance of contributing to the project also required responding to questions from the service in relation to the agronomic qualities and sanitary risks linked to the urine-based fertiliser.

It took a long process of discussion and consultation (three years, during 2018-2020) to bring together the different actors concerned around the SUM project and to validate a scenario accepted by all (in October 2020), taking into account the constraints and possibilities of the different actors. A structure played an important role within the City of Paris in this process: the **Mission Résilience**, a suborganisation of the City’s General Secretariat⁵. Its entry into the stakeholders’ play in 2020 was an important step in opening

⁵ Created in 2015, the Mission Résilience had the mission of coordinating the urban resilience strategy of the City of Paris adopted in 2017 and the public policies resulting from it. The Mission Résilience was integrated in 2022 in the « Pôle Résilience, prospective, recherche et innovation » (Resilience, Foresight, Research and Innovation Unit) attached to the « Direction de la Transition Ecologique et du Climat » (DTEC), created that same year.

up the closed silos of the municipal Departments. In 2020, this structure oversaw a collective process of discussion and decision-making around the project at the scale of the city, in concert with P&MA. The Mission Résilience was an offshoot of the City's General Secretariat. As a result of this situation, a project involving several different departments could be effectively coordinated.

Another group of actors was associated with the design phase of the project: the **actors selected for the building of the lots** (real estate developers, social housing companies and linked teams: architects, engineering companies, etc.). Asked to integrate the instructions related to urine collection into their building projects, they also sometimes had a dialogue with P&MA and its project management assistance group, in order to share their questions and constraints, and to develop projects taking them into account

3.4 Socio-technical choices made and reasons for them

Over the 2019-2020 period, P&MA and its project management assistance group have developed (in conjunction with the City of Paris) a master plan for SUM at SVDP proposing four scenarios, one of which including a variant.

The master plan proposes to collect urine through urine diversion flush toilets (in housing buildings and other equipment), as well as some dry urinals (in equipment).

Concerning the urine treatment, it is suggested (as did the feasibility study in 2018) to transform the urine in a local plant at SVDP through a nitrification-distillation process. This process was developed by the company Vuna Nexus in Switzerland and allows to produce a concentrated fertiliser (5% of the initial volume), the Aurin®⁶. This choice of treatment is justified by the fact that this process makes it possible to transform urine into fertiliser, with volumes reduced by twenty. Volumes needed to be subsequently transported by truck outside of SVDP in order to be used on plantations of the City of Paris (in its Horticultural production centre at Rungis, see 3.7) can thus be significantly reduced with this treatment.

Four scenarios of urine collection at SVDP (one with a variant) are studied in the master plan, involving volumes of urine to be collected and infrastructures to be put in place of variable scale and nature. In the first two scenarios, urine is collected across the entire ZAC (Zone d'aménagement concerté; integrated development zone) (10 lots). They differ in the urine transport methods: through a pressure network for scenario 1, via a mainly gravity network supplemented by a pressure network for scenario 2. Scenarios 3a and 3b envisage urine collection on 7 or 8 lots, with a mainly gravity network, supplemented by one or two pressure pipes. Scenario 4 consists of collecting urine on only one lot (Pinard) and treating it on site. Depending on the scenarios considered, the volume collected ranges from 0.3 m³/day for collection on a single lot to 1.9 m³/d for collection on the 10 lots of the ZAC, with more or less significant associated equipment.

⁶ Aurin® fertiliser is authorized for sale in Switzerland since 2018.

These scenarios are the subject of a multi-criteria analysis in the master plan, taking into account six aspects: 1) Scale of urine collection, 2) Level of experimentation (mono or multidimensional), 3) Economic viability of the project (outlets), 4) Level of risks linked to the project (from a functional, financial point of view, etc.), 5) Ease of operational implementation (technical constraints linked to the execution of the work, the public or private status of used spaces, etc.), and 6) Ease of operation for the urine collection, transport and treatment system. The relevance of the four scenarios was evaluated from these different criteria.

This comparative analysis of different urine collection scenarios carried out in the master plan led in 2019-2020 to a process of discussion and then collective choices between the different operational actors involved (P&MA and services of the City of Paris), brought together in a technical committee for this purpose. Ultimately, one of the two most ambitious scenarios, scenario 2 (see Figure 4), was chosen by the different actors.

Figure 4 Scenario 2 of urine collection (in the entire district, via a mainly gravity network)

In the end, the elected officials of the City of Paris were asked to reach a decision during the SVDP steering committee of October 2020 on three points: the validation or not of the SUM project at SVDP, the selection of a scenario, and the system management mode.

In order to guide elected officials in their arbitration, the Resilience Mission wrote a note, in conjunction with the various Departments of the City of Paris and P&MA. This note presented each scenario and explained the reasons leading the technical committee to favour scenario 2 over the others. This preference was motivated by different criteria: the ambition to test a urine separate management system on the scale of an entire district, the desire to experiment with different technical possibilities (urine collection by gravity

network and under pressure), issues of functionality of the system (a mainly gravity network is more robust and simpler to exploit than a pressure one), and concern for economic viability. Elected officials validated the SUM project at SVDP and selected scenario 2; an ambitious one, since it aims at collecting urine on the scale of the entire district.

3.5 Economic aspects: a support of AESN essential for the implementation of the project

Investments linked to the SUM project at SVDP are financed by different stakeholders. Equipment inside buildings (urine diversion flush toilets and collection pipes) are the responsibility of private or public operators (real estate developers and social housing companies). The urine transport network and the treatment plant are financed by the City of Paris, which will own them and manage their exploitation (see 3.6).

In 2018, the regional public structure Agence de l'Eau Seine-Normandie (AESN, "Seine-Normandie Water Agency") decided to subsidize, as part of its 11th "Water & climate" program over 2019-2024, the investments linked to pilot projects of urine source separation on its territory. This will be the case at SVDP. The AESN has also chosen to grant differentiated aid depending on whether it concerns public or private equipment (up to 80% of investment costs for public actors, 40% for private actors).

The SUM project at SVDP implies additional investments regarding a usual sewage infrastructure, which the City of Paris and other stakeholders (real estate developers and social housing companies) would not necessarily have made if there had not been subsidies from the AESN.

The investment costs (before subsidies) for public collection and treatment equipment were evaluated in 2021 as follows: network (€330,000), factory (€500,000), purchase of the site where the factory will be located (€170,000), fertiliser spreading equipment for the DEVE (between €10,000 and €20,000).

Note that the master plan produced in 2019-2020 showed that the cost of the treatment plant (estimated between €200 and €500k depending on the quantity of urine to be treated) would have represented the most important budgetary item regardless of the scenario chosen (from 1 to 10 lots), and that it was decreasing according to the size of the factory. This aspect weighed in favour of a large-scale scenario, in order to achieve economies of scale.

Regarding operating costs of the SUM system, which should be covered by the DPE, the master plan showed that an economic balance on operation was possible, if the DPE "resold" the urine-based fertiliser produced at the SVDP to the DEVE at the current price of fertiliser purchase for the « Centre de Production Horticole de Rungis » (CPH – Horticultural Production Center of Rungis), on plantations from which it is planned to use the urine-based fertiliser (see 3.7). This evaluation was a decisive aspect in favour of the

involvement of the two services concerned (DPE and DEVE) in the operation of the system and the use of urine-based fertiliser.

3.6 The decision of the City of Paris to pilot the operation of the entire system, with support of private companies: debates and motivations

In 2019-2020, debates took place between the different stakeholders on the future mode of management of SUM system: should its operation be implemented by public or private actors? At the beginning of 2020, The City of Paris finally decided to become the owner not only of the urine collection network, but also of the treatment plant, and to be the pilot of the operation of the entire system (transport, treatment and valorisation).

Several reasons motivated this choice. The allocation by the AESN of greater subsidies in case of investment and project management by public actors favoured the choice of acquisition of equipment and of management of their operation by The City of Paris. Moreover, being the owner and the manager of the entire SUM system (except devices inside buildings) allows the City to keep control of the project, while simplifying its operation, by limiting the actors involved.

However, the City of Paris is considering awarding public contracts aimed at initially entrusting the operation of the network and/or power plant to private actors. Indeed, agents of the Service Technique de l'Eau et de l'Assainissement (STEA, "Technical Water and Sanitation Service") of the DPE, which operates the Parisian sanitation network, have expressed concerns about the prospect of operating this new system. One option studied by the City would be to entrust SUM system's operation to an external actor initially, to train STEA's agents during this time in the operation of the SUM system, then to reinternalize its operation within the City.

The City of Paris thus plans to launch a public tender at the end of 2025 in order to delegate the operation of the treatment plant and of the urine collection network to a private company. It should be noted that this tender may lead several competing companies to offer a variety of urine treatment solutions, with the production of different fertilisers.

3.7 An internal use of the fertiliser on City's plantations: initial outlets, which could be expanded in presence of market authorization

The question of outlets for the urine-based fertiliser produced at SVDP was in 2018-2019, in the beginning of the design phase of the SUM project, one of the unresolved issues. The commercial use of a fertiliser requires, from a regulatory point of view, obtaining a market authorization from the French « Agence Nationale de Sécurité Alimentaire de l'Alimentation » (ANSES, National Food Safety Agency). But it was not existing yet in France for urine-based fertilisers. The internal use of fertiliser, on plantations of the City

of Paris, does not require this authorization. Using urine-based fertiliser on the City's plantations therefore appeared in 2020 to the City of Paris as the easiest solution to initially implement.

For the moment, it is planned to use the fertiliser which will be produced at SVDP on plantations of the « Centre de Production Horticole de Rungis » (CPH – Horticultural Production Centre of Rungis)⁷, and maybe on certain green lawns of the City of Paris. A first series of experiments with the Aurin® urine-based fertiliser, which interests the City notably for its concentrated and stabilised aspects, were carried out by DEVE agents in 2023, to test its agronomic effectiveness on different types of plantations, grown in the CPH greenhouses. The results overall were positive for certain types of plants and less convincing for some types of plants. A second series of experiments began in 2025 and will continue in 2026, with the goal to test the fertiliser on plants on nurseries and on green lawns.

Let us also mention here the recent developments regarding market authorizations for urine-based fertilisers and bio stimulants for agriculture in Europe and in France. As concerns the Aurin® fertiliser, developed by the company Vuna Nexus it has been marketable in Switzerland since 2018. Then, in the European Union states, a first market authorization was delivered in Austria in 2022. More recently, a market authorization was delivered in France in 2024 for the Aurin® produced at the European Spatial Agency in Paris 15th. Since 2022, the company Toopi Organics has also obtained market authorization for its bio stimulant Lactopi Start® in France and in five other European countries.

If the City of Paris decides to produce at SVDP a fertiliser that benefits from market authorization, it might be able to expand outlets for the fertiliser beyond municipal plantations and green spaces. Examples of outlets could be selling the product to Parisians, and/or to farmers in the city or the region, but this raises the question of the organisation to be put in place for such an expansion, since the marketing of products is not one of the City's missions and the urine-based fertiliser distribution channel remains to be created.

3.8 A system under construction since 2021: current situation and issues raised

After deconstruction work on certain buildings over the 2018-2020 period (see Figure 2), construction work on the SVDP district began in 2021. It should be completed in 2029. The wastewater collection networks, and in particular that for urine, were built in 2021-2022. The buildings of the different lots will be built gradually from 2024 to 2029. The urine treatment plant should be built in 2026-2027. This new phase of the SUM project, the construction phase, leads to the introduction of new actors in the implementation of

⁷ Note that the DEVE uses very little fertiliser in the gardens of the City of Paris. Green waste (pruning and mowing residues) and mulching are sufficient as input for gardens.

the SVDP project (such as construction companies). Relations between the different actors are now focused around the issues of correctly constructing the SUM system (Figure 5).

Figure 5 System of stakeholders involved in the construction phase (2021-2029)

In this context, a stake for P&MA and its project management assistance group, in particular Tilia company, is to closely accompany and supervise the teams involved in the construction of the SUM system, at several levels: City of Paris, real estate operators and social landlords, prime contractor teams and construction companies, which will build an unusual system which has certain specificities and which may raise questions from them.

There were no major problems during the building of the urine collection network in 2021-2022. The stakeholders found themselves confronted with certain specific technical questions, notably about manholes to be put in place to enable the monitoring and maintenance of a urine collection network (which cannot be visited, to guarantee a form of airtightness and avoid odor problems), and about slopes of the network to be respected (to avoid problems of urine stagnation and struvite precipitation). But solutions were found, and the network was built without difficulty.

The buildings' construction phase at SVDP began in 2024 and will take place up to 2029. Urine diversion flush toilets and collection pipes will be installed gradually in the (public and private) buildings.

P&MA has asked social landlords and real estate developers to equip their buildings with urine diversion flush toilets, while allowing them to choose the model. It's the Laufen Save!

Toilet model which has been selected so far (the Wostman EcoFlush model has also been considered, but not retained) (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 The Laufen Save! Urine diversion toilets model

Normally, urine diversion flush toilets should be installed in almost all the apartments (around 600). It is also planned to install them in shops and public and private facilities at SVDP, where possible. The choices are made based on two criteria: (i) the possibility of connecting apartments and other facilities to the public urine collection network; (ii) and the adaptation of toilets to users. For example, the nursery school will not be equipped with urine diversion toilets, as there are currently no models suitable for young children, but the primary school will be equipped with separative toilets.

It should be noted that the installation of urine collection networks inside the buildings of the different lots raises certain issues, requiring to find solutions adapted to each case. The urine separation networks require indeed, to function properly, slopes greater than or equal to 3%, and that there are no bends at 90°, except in rare exceptions. Taking these constraints into account have raised difficulties on certain buildings currently under construction. Similarly, the altimetry of the lots and the altitude of the public urine collection network have raised problems in certain cases in order to connect internal pipes of the buildings to the public network.

It will be therefore necessary to install two lifting pumps in two lots currently under construction ("Petit" and "Pinard"), to connect internal pipes to the public urine collection network. In two other lots ("Lepage" and "Lelong"), the (public and private) building owners decided to maintain internal gravity urine collection networks (considered simpler in terms of operation), and not to connect certain apartments or shops on the ground floor, which would have required the installation of an additional lifting pump.

The conception of the urine treatment plant (which will be built in 2026-2027 and owned by the City of Paris) has also raised some issues. To avoid weakening the foundations of the “Chaufferie” building, where the plant will be located, the prime contractor team ultimately recommended in 2024 not to install the storage tanks for the urine-based fertiliser inside the building but outside, in the garden. This required changing the plans for the urine collection network and finding an appropriate place for the tanks, to make it possible pumping and transporting the fertiliser outside the district of SVDP, in order to use it in plantations of the City of Paris.

An innovative project, such as the SUM project at SVDP, involves constraints and raises specific issues, as the examples mentioned show. While some issues can be anticipated, others often arise along the way (case of lifting pumps to be installed on certain lots, or fertiliser storage tanks to be moved), requiring the public and private stakeholders involved a capacity to find solutions together, and an ability to adapt to unforeseen events and problems that arise over time.

On this point, an interesting aspect of the project of SVDP is the fact that the large size of the project and the long construction schedule for the district (2021-2029) allow to a certain extent to benefit from (relative) feedback from the lots already built, and to anticipate certain problems for the new lots to be built.

3.9 Stakes linked to the future operation of the SUM system

In parallel with this construction of the SUM system, the City of Paris and P&MA still work on other subjects which will need to be explored and which require choices to be made, notably concerning the form of the future operating system to be put in place.

We note in 3.6 that the City of Paris decided to be the pilot of the operation of the SUM system for the following parts: transport, treatment of urines and valorisation of the fertiliser. The City however plans to entrust firstly the operation of the urine treatment plant and of the urine collection network to an external actor for an initial period. In parallel, the City is considering to train STEA’s agents during this time in the operation of the SUM system, and then to reinternalize its operation within the City. Regarding the use of urine-based fertiliser on plantations and lawns of the City of Paris, this also requires training the DEVE’s agents in its use. The different aspects of operation mentioned above will therefore involve various public and private players, necessitating their coordination and the training of them.

For the SUM system to work properly, urine diversion toilets’ users must also adapt their practices (this subject is covered in the following section 4), and toilets and urine collection pipes inside the buildings must be properly maintained, by following specific instructions. This maintenance of toilets and pipes will involve various people (residents, but also toilet maintenance staff, building maintenance staff, plumbers, etc.). All these people need to

be informed and trained. A stake is therefore for P&MA and the City of Paris to work together, with developers and social landlords in particular, to set up such initiatives.

We have also mentioned the fact that some buildings will be fitted with lifting pumps to connect their internal pipes to the public urine collection network. Such pumps need to be properly maintained. Who will do this? And who will intervene if there is a problem with the operation of the SUM system in buildings, owned by other (public and private) actors than the City of Paris?

All the issues raised are major challenges for the smooth running of the SUM project, and will require P&MA and the City of Paris to find solutions in conjunction with the other stakeholders involved in the coming years.

4. The challenge of adapting users' practices to toilets: results of a survey, support issues and planned actions

4.1 The survey conducted in 2024: context, process and profiles of respondents

The City of Paris has made SVDP a collaborative urban planning laboratory, with the wish to involve the future residents of SVDP in the design of their district. Various initiatives have been initiated for this purpose. One of the buildings of SVDP, the « Lepage » building, developed by the social housing company Paris Habitat, will be a participatory housing; the future owners of the 23 apartments of this building have been known since 2020 and have participated during the 2021-2024 period in the design of their apartments and of common spaces. The social housing companies RIVP and Paris Habitat also decided to involve the future residents of two social housing buildings ("Chaufferie" and "Petit") in the design of their housing. This initiative is very original, because the tenants of Parisian social housing are normally only known a few months before the building's delivery. Usually, they cannot therefore contribute to this type of collaborative urban planning approach. In the case of Chaufferie and Petit buildings, a panel of 40 future residents was set up in 2020. Since 2021, this panel regularly participates in workshops with social housing companies and design offices, to consider collectively the different dimensions of the social housing buildings that will be built. These workshops cover various subjects: quality criteria for apartments, definition of collective spaces and services, energy savings, etc.

The fact that some future residents of SVDP are known before the commissioning of the district is a particularly interesting aspect. This situation indeed makes it possible to collect and analyse the point of view of these future residents on the SUM project at SVDP.

The City of Paris also therefore decided to carry out in 2024 with the OCAPI team a survey via online questionnaire among these future residents aimed at collecting qualitative information on: 1) their current toilet practices, 2) their perceptions and questions

regarding urine diversion flush toilets that they will have to use in their apartments, and more largely regarding the project of valorising urine as fertiliser, and finally, 3) their need for support in the process of appropriating these specific toilets.

The survey took place between January and August 2024. We received a total of 46 responses to the survey (sent to 63 households), which is a very good result in terms of participation. The responses provided by the two categories of residents (participatory housing/social housing) were generally similar. Therefore, we decided to process and analyze them together, except for a few specific questions.

As concerns profiles of respondents, 59% are women, 41% men. This balanced distribution is interesting, as it enables to gather the views of both genders on their toilet practices and their acceptance of urine diversion flush toilets. The fact that 19 men responded to the survey is also interesting, as the survey includes two questions specific to men⁸.

The most represented age group among respondents is 35-49 (59%), followed by 50-64 (28%). The majority are working people (83%). The most represented socio-professional category is “managers and higher intellectual occupations” (50%), followed by intermediate professions (29%). A majority of respondents (69%) have children in their household, with ages from toddlers to young adults.

Are the age groups and socio-professional categories of respondents representative of the future inhabitants of SVDP? Knowing this would give an idea of how representative the respondents and their answers are. In any case, it’s important to keep in mind that survey respondents are mainly working people in upper and middle socio-professional categories. The results must be interpreted in this light. The following other aspects should be kept in mind regarding the profiles of the survey respondents.

First, these are individuals who applied and were selected either to live in participatory housing or to form a panel of future social housing residents engaged in a collaborative urban planning approach. In both cases, these individuals, due to the processes they engaged in, may have profiles that are not representative of the “average citizen.” Furthermore, these are individuals who have had the opportunity to access information about the urine collection and recycling project at SVDP, through the various participatory processes they have been involved in since 2021.

Several specific information and awareness-raising actions on the SUM project aimed at the panels of future residents were indeed deployed by P&MA and its “urine” project management assistance group, in conjunction with social landlords, during the last years. Two workshops were thus organized in 2023. Flyers as well as a video explaining the project and its challenges were also developed and diffused. Finally, a model of urine diversion flush toilets (the Laufen company’s Save! Model, which will be used at SVDP)

⁸ As for their current toilet practices: do they sometimes urinate sitting down at home and how often? And as for adopting this practice as part of the future use of separate toilets: does it bother them or not?

was also installed in 2023 in the meeting room “La Lingerie” in the SVDP district, to allow people to test the toilets. These various actions may have had an impact on survey respondents and led them to change their perception of the project.

All of the aspects described must be taken into consideration when interpreting the survey results, which may therefore contain certain biases. However, the survey provides instructive results with the aim of developing an approach to raising awareness and supporting future residents and other users of urine diversion flush toilets in the implementation of appropriate practices for the smooth running of the SUM project at SVDP, and more broadly for other projects in other places.

4.2 Main lessons from the survey

4.2.1 A favorable reception of the project, but from people aware of associated issues

The SUM project is well received by 80% of respondents, and neutrally received by 20%. No respondent says to be opposed to the project. The reasons given to justify a positive reception are mainly ecological motivations and interest in taking part in an innovative project. Those who welcome the project neutrally express their need to see whether or not the system works, skepticism about the active participation of all residents in the project, or indifference to the project. Concerning the future use of urine diversion toilets in their future apartments, 40% of respondents are very enthusiastic about this idea and 38% rather enthusiastic. 15% are indifferent and 6% rather concerned, with questions about toilets' efficiency, odors, etc.

With regard to SUM project information and awareness-raising initiatives aimed at pre-identified future residents, 67% of respondents took part in at least one of the two workshops organized in 2023 on the SUM project. 53% viewed the video produced on the project prior to the survey. 41% also tested the Save! Toilet model installed at La Lingerie in SVDP. Feedback on the toilets is generally positive, with the model considered to be close to conventional toilets, easy to use and without major changes for the user.

This is one of the very positive results of the survey: the positive reception of the SUM project and of separative toilets by respondents to the survey. The various information and awareness-raising actions on the SUM project have reached a significant number of the people surveyed, with potentially positive effects on their view of the project.

4.2.2 Some people ready to adapt their practices, with significant stakes on this subject

Interrogated on what they flush down the toilets, besides excreta and toilet paper, respondents said: vomit (74%), cleaning water (45%), food scraps (31%) and DIY waste (17%). As for toilets cleaning products used, white vinegar is the most frequently cited (52%), followed by eco-labelled products (46%) and classic products such as Canard WC

(41%). Bleach (30%), baking soda (26%), blocks for toilet bowls (15%) and citric acid (11%) are also used by certain of them.

Some respondents thus pour materials and products into their current toilets which could harm the proper recovery of urine at SVDP. The use of natural and ecological cleaning products seems to be already anchored in the habits of half of them, but almost half use conventional biocidal products that are contraindicated for urine diversion toilets. In addition, 37% use both ecological and conventional products, so that one is not exclusive of the other. Finally, citric acid, recommended for the maintenance of the urine evacuation system, is the least cited product (11%). The challenges of adapting practices appear therefore to be significant.

Another interesting result of this survey is the fact that most masculine respondents said urinate more or less frequently in a seated position at home: 25% say they do so all the time, 25% frequently and 40% occasionally. Only 10% never do it. So, it seems that this issue (urinating while seated for men using urine diversion toilets), often presented as critical, is perhaps not so critical after all.

The vast majority of respondents (90%) seem ok with the idea of having to comply with a certain number of instructions for the proper use of separative toilets (not use nor throw biocidal products, etc.). The instruction that bothers the most is the fact that men have to urinate in a seated position (26% of men say this is a problem for them⁹).

Changing users' practices, both in terms of what they flush down the toilet and in terms of the products they use to maintain toilets, are thus key issues raised by the survey. Sitting in a seated position for men also appears to be an adaptation issue, although less so than expected. The vast majority of people surveyed (90%) seem willing to adapt their practices to enable the project to run smoothly.

4.2.3 Inform and support residents and other users: some various needs

54.5% of respondents said they would like to receive additional information beyond the one already received on the SUM project, whereas 45.5% said they did not. Requests for information included both practical information on toilets' use and maintenance, as well as general information on the SUM system. Regarding means of disseminating information, flyers appeared to be the most popular form (63%), followed by emails (48%) and workshops (37%). Workshops are considered useful for both adults and children. This raises the question: should specific actions be planned for children?

The support measures suggested in the survey (distribution/sale of suitable cleaning products for separative toilets, annual toilets' maintenance visits, hotline or contact person for toilets-related problems or questions) are considered very useful or useful by a

⁹ This result may raise questions, since only 10% of male respondents say they never urinate sitting down at home.

majority of respondents. They were also keen to find out more about the SUM project. All the actions suggested in this sense (discovery of the plant; newsletter on the project; distribution/sale of bottles of urine-based fertilizer, etc.) were deemed very useful or useful by a majority of them.

The survey shows that a balance has to be found to keep people informed without saturating them. A variety of information formats are deemed pertinent (flyers, e-mails, workshops, etc.): diversifying them is likely to reach the greatest number of people. Respondents expressed a desire for practical support in their use of separative toilets, but also a desire to discover more broadly the SUM project (visit of plant, etc.). The challenge ahead for SVDP's project carriers is to design an awareness-raising and support system that integrates these different aspects.

4.3 What change support system should be designed for users?

4.3.1 Planned actions at SVDP

The City of Paris and P&MA are considering the system to be implemented to best support future residents and other users in the adoption of separative toilets and to promote the smooth running of the SUM project. It should be noted that the regional public structure Agence de l'Eau Seine-Normandie (AESN), which subsidizes the SUM project at SVDP, includes a change support axe in its subsidy policy.

Among support measures currently being developed, work has been initiated in 2024 by P&MA with the company Laufen (designer and seller of the Save! Model of urine diversion toilets which will be installed at SVDP) to design signage that will appear on the toilets. A more detailed user guide concerning the use and maintenance of these specific toilets will also be produced and provided to the future residents and the managers of buildings and facilities at SVDP.

It is also planned to create a post of «gestionnaire de quartier» («neighbourhood manager») at SVDP. This person, who will be recruited in 2026, will be trained in “good practices” for using the various innovative environmental devices that will be implemented at SVDP (in terms of energy, regarding urine diversion flush toilets, etc.). One of the missions of the «neighbourhood manager» will be to raise awareness and support residents and other users of SVDP in the use of these devices. However, the neighbourhood manager's missions will be multiple, and its exact role in supporting users of separative toilets remains to be defined. In any case, the neighbourhood manager will need to be formed so that it can itself raise awareness and support users.

The City of Paris and P&MA are also considering other awareness-raising and change support actions concerning the SUM project: workshops for building managers in 2026, and, once the SVDP district delivered (in 2026-2027), public events around the urine treatment plant and the fertiliser produced (visits of the plant, festive events, etc.). In the

City of Paris, it is also planned to raise awareness and train agents of the DEVE (Department of Green Spaces and the Environment) in the use of fertiliser.

4.3.2 Questions still to be answered

Other topics are currently under consideration.

Should there be a place at SVDP where residents and managers of buildings and facilities can buy suitable cleaning products for separate toilets? Or should these products even be distributed freely (in particular citric acid which must be used to maintain the urine evacuation system)?

Should there be an annual inspection visit to the toilets, as there is for boilers, for example? But who's going to do it, and to pay for it? What procedure should be put in place in case of problems (odours, blocked toilets)? Who should be contacted, and who will intervene? Plumbers are today not trained in the specificities of separate toilets. Should an explanatory document be produced for them, or should plumbers be trained? But who's going to do it?

The existence of a person to contact in case of questions and/or problems relating to toilets also seems to be a very useful measure for the smooth running of the SUM project. Is it the neighbourhood manager who should assume this role, which requires training? If not, who else?

More broadly, there is the question of financing the change support measures to be put in place. The AESN will finance some actions in the coming years through its grants for the SUM project at SVDP. However, this funding is one-off, not sustainable over time. The following question therefore arises: how can change support measures be financed over the long term, and how can this funding be distributed among the various stakeholders involved in the project (City of Paris, building and equipment managers, residents, etc.)?

4.4 Diversity and turnover of users: two challenges to be considered

The users of separate toilets at SVDP will be very diverse. Regarding habitation buildings, the apartments will be occupied by various residents, either owners or tenants, with different profiles (ages, social categories, presence of children or not, etc.). Beyond habitation buildings, businesses and other institutions (school, gymnasium, arts and creative centre, etc.) will be also equipped with urine diversion toilets. Furthermore, SVDP will accommodate specific populations: two shared apartments will be dedicated to populations with visual impairments and other disabilities, and an emergency shelter will accommodate people in vulnerable situations. A challenge regarding the support measures to be put in place therefore consists of considering this diversity of users at

SVDP and designing measures adapted to the specificities of the different categories of users.

Furthermore, it's not just users of toilets who need to be addressed to raise their awareness and to be formed, but also everyone involved in the management and maintenance of urine diversion toilets. These include many stakeholders: toilet maintenance staff in public and private facilities, building managers, but also neighbourhood manager, plumbers, etc.

Beyond the diversity of stakeholders involved, another challenge is the turnover of residents and other users at SVDP. Here again, it is necessary to design long-term awareness-raising and training initiatives that consider the departures and arrivals of new people in the neighbourhood (concerning residents, but also the staff who manage the buildings, maintain the toilets, etc.).

5. Lessons and recommendations from the SVDP case on governance frameworks and on barriers and drivers

This part aims to highlight lessons and recommendations issued from the analysis of the SUM project at SVDP, in terms of possible governance frameworks and of stakes and drivers identified. The outcomes of the analysis were discussed in the frame of a stakeholder workshop on the 04.11.2024 that had been organised by ENPC and the City of Paris. The participants covered the different stakeholders involved in the Saint-Vincent-de-Paul project. The results of the discussion fed into the following recommendations.

5.1 The interest of “niches” for the experimentation of source separation

The Multi-Level Perspective (MLP) approach highlights the fact that “niches” are contexts conducive to the emergence of innovative practices, before their (possible) wider diffusion within the dominant socio-technical regime (Geels, 2002). This hypothesis is verified in France for excreta source separation.

Indeed, we observe in France up to the 2010s first experimentations of this practice in “niches” such as ecological centres, participatory housings, etc. (Joveniaux, de Gouvello and Legrand, 2021). At the end of the 2010s, source separation began to be incorporated into larger scale development projects, led by conventional city making actors, such as the City of Paris and the public developer P&MA for the SVDP project.

However, we can note on this subject that if the district development project at SVDP can be considered as conventional from a certain point of view (from the actors who carry it), it is nevertheless a project fitting into the French ÉcoQuartier labelling process (Eco-district). From this point of view, we can consider that Eco-districts also constitute potential “niches”, favourable to experimenting with innovative practices in terms of socio-ecological transition.

Lessons and recommendations n°1

Supporting source separation experimentation in “niches” (ecological centres, participatory housings, Eco-districts, etc.), in order to initiate the development of the practice in further countries.

5.2 The key role of public actors in the implementation of such projects

The study of the SUM project at SVDP highlights the key role of two categories of public actors in favour of the implementation of this project.

- Actors implied in the genesis and design of the project at SVDP:
 - **Two deputy mayors of Paris (in charge of sanitation and urbanism)**, who were at the origin of the SUM project in 2018,
 - **The City of Paris and its public development company Paris Métropole Aménagement (P&MA)**, which implement the project. The strong involvement of the City of Paris in the SUM project is to be noted. The City has in fact decided to own the urine collection network and treatment plant, which will thus be public equipment, and to pilot the operation of the system¹⁰.

- Actors financially supporting the project:
 - **The regional Water Agency (AESN)**, which highly subsidizes the SUM project (up to 80% for public equipment and 40% for private equipment). This financial support from the AESN motivated the City of Paris and the private actors involved in the SVDP development project to embark on this experiment, by reducing the investment costs with the project.

If we broaden the focus of our analysis beyond the SVDP case, by regarding the larger emerging dynamics around excreta source separation in France, we can also observe the fact that public actors play a decisive role in favour of source separation projects' implementation, both financially and institutionally:

- In the Paris region and as part of its 2019-2024 Water and Climate program, **the AESN** is subsidizing other projects: The Restaurant 211 in Paris, the C15B building in Palaiseau (Essonne), etc.;
- In other regions in France, **some local authorities and/or state bodies** also support source separation projects, led by private or public stakeholders. For example, the participative housing L'Ôdôberge in Dol-de-Bretagne (Ille-et-Vilaine), in service since 2023, where urine and faeces are collected separately for agricultural recovery purposes, received financial support from the Bretagne region and the Loire-Bretagne Water Agency. The Fumainerie association in Bordeaux (Gironde), which has since 2020 a role of territorial animator in favour of excreta valorisation, also benefits from financial support from Bordeaux Métropole, the Department of Gironde and the Regional Directorate for Environment, Development and Housing (DREAL) of New Aquitaine (state body). The start-up Toopi Organics, founded in 2019 and based in

¹⁰ However, the operation of the network and/or the factory should be done with the help of private companies (see 3.6).

Loupiac-de-la-Réole (Gironde), which produces agricultural bio stimulants from urine, has obtained state's subsidies of several million euros to develop its activity.

Note that, if we have observed for around ten years in France more frequent financial and institutional support for source separation projects from local authorities, the municipalities that directly implement such projects, as the City of Paris, are still rare in France.

Lessons and recommendations n°2

Political support of local elected officials is a key lever for the implementation of source separation projects (as shows the SVDP case).

Financial and institutional supports from public actors (local authorities and/or state bodies) are also essential levers for these projects. Indeed, they require investments in new infrastructures and equipment, and also advice and support to overcome other obstacles, as regulatory ones.

Public actors have the capacity, through their subsidy policies, to influence the form of the projects that emerge. For example, the AESN, by financing up to 80% for public equipment and up to 40% for private ones, shows its desire to strongly support public projects¹¹.

Do public actors have a particular responsibility that should push them to play a pilot role in favour of more sustainable practices' experimentation? The City of Paris seems to consider that it is the case, by deciding to initiate and pilot the SUM system operation at SVDP.

Long-term support for projects is however never guaranteed. As concerns the SUM project at SVDP, it will require, with each change of elected officials, to re-convince the new ones of the interest of the project, so as not to see the dynamic put in place fade and to favour the longevity and the success of the project.

5.3 Design and implement an innovative and transversal project: the need for time and for an integrate approach

Managing to align the different stakeholders involved around an innovative and transversal project such as SUM at SVDP in order to reach a concerted project, requires time. During the design phase of the SVDP project, it took three years of discussion and concertation (2018-2020) between the different structures: The City of Paris and P&MA, and, within the City of Paris, between the different departments involved, to achieve the validation of a scenario accepted by all and taking into account the constraints and possibilities of the different actors.

Urine source separation and valorisation projects deal with different sectors (sanitation, urbanism, green spaces or agriculture...), raise transversal issues and involve multiple

¹¹ Indeed, the AESN considers that public actors, and in particular local authorities, responsible for water and sanitation management in France, have an important role to play in the development of the practice.

structures and departments. Thus, at the City of Paris, the following departments (among others) are involved: Waste management and water Department (DPE), Green Spaces and Environment Department (DEVE), Urbanism Department (DU), Ecological Transition and Climate Department (DTEC). A transversal approach is needed to design together collective projects, with integrator and coordinator actors.

In the case of the SUM project at SVDP, two structures in particular have played an important integrator and coordinator role during the design phase (2018-2020):

- The Mission Résilience of the City of Paris: this offshoot of the City's General Secretariat, entered into the play of actors in 2020, oversaw a collective and transversal process of discussion and decision-making between the different departments of the municipality;
- The project management assistance group of P&MA: this group, selected by P&MA in 2019 and compounded of four companies with varied skills (see 3.3), played also an important role to design a SUM project required a transversal approach. Note that the group continues to support P&MA and the various stakeholders involved in the SUM project during its construction phase.

The SVDP case also highlights the following issue regarding the need for an integrated approach: the public and private parts of the project must be thought of together, because the choices made on ones have interactions on others, whether for the system to be designed or for its future operation. For example, at SVDP, the altimetry of the public urine collection network required the installation of lift pumps on two building lots. These are complex technical devices to manage. Who will maintain them or intervene in the event of problems? Since these pumps are located in private areas, it is not in principle the responsibility of the City of Paris to operate them. However, their proper functioning is important for the well-running of the project.

Lessons and recommendations n°3

- Time is needed to align stakeholders and to design together innovative and transversal projects.*
- There is also a need for integrator and coordinator actors.*
- Public and private parts of projects must be thought out together, because socio-technical choices made on ones have interactions on others, for the design as well as for the operation of separate excreta management systems*

5.4 The possibility of “reversibility” and the ability to adapt gradually the project: two conditions favoring action and well-running of experiment

In the SVDP case (but also in other projects in France), the “reversibility” of the project was a condition favouring action. Given the uncertainty regarding success of the experiment, the system chosen is reversible, offering the possibility of reverting to classical toilets and to the public sewage network. This condition made it easier to convince the different actors to join the project.

Like all experimental projects, source separation projects can face unexpected technical problems or social acceptability difficulties. They require dealing with uncertainties, for example in terms of markets and regulations, which do not yet or only partially integrate excreta valorisation practices. The stakeholders must accommodate these constraints and uncertainties when implementing projects. Implementing innovative projects is an open process, with possible adaptations along the way. Some solutions can be provisory and likely to evolve. Two examples concerning the SUM project at SVDP:

- The urine-based fertiliser produced at the SVDP should be used on plantations of the Rungis Horticultural Production Centre. This choice is motivated by the fact that the City of Paris is interested in the idea of testing this new type of fertiliser on its plantations, but also due to the current absence of marketing authorization for the product in France. However, if an authorization is delivered in the coming years (which will be probably the case), the fertiliser could then be sold to farmers and other users. First internal outlets within the City have been found for urine-based fertiliser, the current situation not allowing it to be sold, but outlets could potentially be expanded subsequently.
- Concerning the collection network and the treatment plant of urine, the City of Paris will probably, at the beginning, contract external actors in order to operate it, because of the novelty of the system and because the agents of the STEA have expressed concerns about the prospect of operating it. But the operation of the SUM system could be reinternalized later, once the system has been tested and municipal agents have been trained.

Lessons and recommendations n°4

- Innovative source separation projects face uncertainties and risks, on technical, social, regulatory and economic aspects. The capacity to be in an iterative trial-and-error approach and to build and adapt the project gradually is a factor of success (and more than that, necessary!).*
- The possibility of system reversibility is a reassuring condition, which favours the commitment of stakeholders in such projects.*
- In an uncertain and evolving context, some solutions can be provisory and likely to change over time (example concerning the SVDP case: possibility of marketing the fertiliser, if an authorization is delivered, etc.).*

- Conversely, some technical choices must be made in time, because it is no longer possible to make them afterwards. Thus, in case of doubt about the acceptability by all users of a SUM project, it is possible to set up a double-piped system inside all buildings, even if a few of them are equipped with dry or flush separation toilets in a first time. It will therefore be possible to gradually extend the experiment to all buildings, already equipped for possible urine separate collection.*

5.5 Projects must be adapted to the specificities of territories (and to the involved stakeholders) to work

We studied the socio-technical choices made for the SUM project at SVDP. But it is worth noting that socio-technical choices made can vary greatly depending on projects. The projects of excreta source separation existing in France are very diversified, at different levels (Joveniaux et al., 2022). The projects vary in the materials collected (urine and/or faeces), the scale of the projects, their forms of territorial embeddedness, the collection, treatment and valorisation chains, the project initiators and the stakeholders involved in the valorisation chain, as well as the associated financing and economic models. This shows that there are many possible options.

There is no single socio-technical solution, single type of valorisation chain or single type of economic model that would be the best and the most appropriate. A project can be implemented and work in one territory, but may not work in another. The projects implemented are relevant and can work if they are adapted to the specificities and challenges of the territories and take into account the characteristics, constraints, motivations and aspirations of the stakeholders involved.

Lessons and recommendations n°5

- It is important to keep in mind that there is no one solution that is better than others, whether on technical aspects or on governance aspects.*
- A determining factor for the success of source separation projects is their adaptation to the specificities of territories (spatial configuration, local issues, etc.), but also to the motivations and constraints of involved stakeholders.*

5.6 Different stages of a project requiring transmission of knowledge and “onboarding” of new stakeholders at each phase

A project is divided into several phases (design/construction/operation), each of which raises specific challenges and issues. Here are examples of challenges and issues linked to different phases in the SUM project at SVDP:

- *Design phase (2018-2020):* the issue of constructing and validating a concerted project between the different stakeholders,

- *Construction phase (2021-2026/2027)*: the need to give clear instructions and to closely supervise and coordinate the companies building the SUM system,
- *Operation phase (>2026/2027)*: the questions of stakeholders' involvement and practices' evolution (residents and other users of urine diversion toilets, teams exploiting the SUM system...).

Stakeholders are partly changing in the different phases, with new ones involved.

The first challenge facing this situation is to “re-board”, at each stage, the new stakeholders (operational actors, users, etc.) entering in the project, and to convince them of the interest of investing in it. It is also needed, in case of change of municipal team, to “re-create” and maintain the political support for the project (see 5.2).

A second and equally important challenge is therefore to ensure the proper transmission of information, knowledge and know-how linked to the project between the different stakeholders involved in the project at a given time, but also to new entrants to each phase of the project. This proper transmission of information is an essential point for the well-running of the project, and means to think about how knowledge can be passed on between stakeholders and from one phase to the next.

The transmission of information is based in part on specific documents to be designed for this purpose (urban planning specifications in the design phase, execution plans in the construction phase, notice of use and maintenance of toilets or pipes in the operation phase, etc.), as well as on structures and actors who can ensure the continuity and/or transfer of information over time.

If we return to the case of SVDP, several initiatives (ongoing or planned) can seem favourable for transmission of knowledge from one phase to another:

- *P&MA's project management assistance mission for the SUM project at SVDP unfolds over time and encompasses the different phases of the project.* This mission was launched in 2019, during the design phase. The project management assistance group currently continues to support the stakeholders during the construction phase of the SUM system, and should probably also do so again during the start of commissioning of it, as part of the approach presented below;
- *P&MA seeks to ensure a good handing over between stakeholders of the development phase and of the commissioning phase of the projects it carries out.* For this purpose, and in case of eco-neighbourhood projects integrating socio-delivered, to support neighbourhood stakeholders in the process of appropriating these innovations. This is what is planned at SVDP, where P&MA plans to support stakeholders in the first years of commissioning of the district (first two a priori) on different subjects, in particular energy management systems, but also SUM;
- It is planned to create a post of «gestionnaire de quartier» («neighbourhood manager») at SVDP. This person will be trained in “good practices” for using the various innovative

environmental devices that will be implemented at SVDP (in terms of energy, regarding urine diversion flush toilets, etc.). One of the missions of the «neighbourhood manager» will be to raise awareness and support residents and other users in the use of these devices. This “neighbourhood manager” will therefore have an important role of transmitting information and supporting users in their use of urine diversion toilets.

Lessons and recommendations n°6

- Ensure good transmission of knowledge between different stakeholders and from one phase of the project to another is an essential issue for the well-running of an innovative project such as SUM, which requires a transfer of new knowledge.**
- The production of documents aimed at guiding stakeholders at the different stages of the project (design/construction/operation) is an important aspect.**
- The transmission of knowledge also requires the presence of structures and actors who ensure continuity between the different phases and who ensure the transmission of information to new participants in the project. On this point, initiatives implemented at the SVDP (such as: project management assistance group whose mission encompasses the different phases of the project, “neighbourhood manager” one of whose missions will be to support users in environmental practices, etc.) can inspire other projects.**
- Beyond the transmission of knowledge, the challenge arises at each stage of the project is to re-mobilize new entrants and to maintain long-term adhesion and support for the project (from different stakeholders and political actors).**

5.7 The need for actions to support users in changing their practices

The involvement of future residents and other users of separate toilets and their appropriation of new practices are crucial for the well-running of separate excreta management projects. It is necessary to plan awareness-raising and support actions for users (residents and others), and a suitable budget to finance them. Neglecting this essential aspect can jeopardize the successful implementation of the projects carried out.

On this point, the survey carried out in 2024 among a panel of future residents at SVDP highlights the following aspects.

We can hypothesize that information and awareness-raising initiatives (workshops, videos, testable toilets, etc.) implemented since 2021 by P&MA, the City of Paris and social landlords among the panel of future residents have had positive effects on their good perception of the project (80% welcome it, the others are neutral but not unfavorable) and their acceptance of the idea to adapt some of their practices (90% are ok with this idea). The continuation and development of this type of actions would therefore be essential in order to promote acceptance of the SUM project by local residents and users, and to ensure that it runs smoothly! The same applies to other separate excreta management projects that could be set up in other places.

The survey also highlights several challenges in adapting the practices of future users of separate toilets, particularly in terms of materials that should not be flushed down into the toilets and in terms of adapted cleaning products to be used. The measures to be put in place to permit the implementation of appropriate practices among residents and other users of SVDP are informative, but also operational. This involves designing a concrete support system for users of toilets (provision of appropriate toilet cleaning products, person to contact in case of problems, etc.).

Beyond questions relating to the use of urine diverting flush toilets, the survey reveals a real curiosity among respondents to know more about the SUM project, how it works, the results obtained, etc. (desire to visit the treatment plant, to use the fertiliser produced from their urine, etc.). Implementing such actions could encourage users of separate toilets to get involved, by enabling them to fully appreciate the stakes involved and the concrete results of their implication.

Finally, the SVDP survey highlights these issues concerning the question of users support:

- the necessity to consider the diversity of the people involved in use and maintenance of toilets (residents with varied profiles, other users, but also staff in charge of maintaining the toilets, plumbers, etc.) and to propose support measures adapted to the specificities and roles of each of them,
- the need for a long-term support system, integrating the problematic of turnover of residents and other actors.

Lessons and recommendations n°7

- The social dimension (involvement of toilet users and adaptation of their practices) is as important as technical issues for the well-running of excreta recovery projects. It is therefore necessary to plan awareness-raising and support actions for toilet users (residents and others) and an appropriate budget to finance them.**
- These actions must include different aspects:** - informative (how to use and maintain the toilets), - operational (concrete actions to support users, as distribution of suitable cleaning products or person to contact in case of problem), - broader discovery of projects (visit of plant, distribution of urine-based fertiliser, etc.).
- Users' information and support system should also integrate these two issues:** - the diversity of people involved in the use and maintenance of toilets, - the change of residents and other actors. These two issues request having actions adapted to the different users. These actions also need to be regularly renewed and lasting over time

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Part B: Analysis and provisional recommendations of case studies

Executive Summary

In the previous deliverable 4.1, a total of 8 case studies were shortlisted out of 55 which were then analysed based on their relevance to the P2Green project. The deliverable was submitted on 31st May 2024.

Following the new updates on the case studies, four more case studies have been analysed. They also follow the study and analysis with the focus on the governance instruments as well as local initiatives to foster the adoption of resource-oriented source separation of waste flows. The selected case studies differ in scale and are focused on the wastewater flows and their reuse and the recovery of nutrients and energy. They emphasize the role of awareness on the decentralised sanitation systems and their benefits to the environment. They are studied with the five categories of governance; mobilise, educate, manage, incentivise and regulate. They are illustrated in the tabular form as in the previous deliverable which also shows the value chain descriptions (Collection, treatment, and fertiliser usage).

1. Introduction

In the previous deliverable 4.1, 8 case studies were studied. They were relevant to P2Green in terms of policies, wastewater management, and resource-oriented sanitation among many more aspects. The cases were studied in terms of collection, logistics and treatment, and fertiliser use.

A first broad search for projects resulted in a list of 55 projects that were examined with the focus to identify practical, and if possible mature examples of the project, which resulted in the choice of the 8 projects, tabulated below. Four additional examples are studied in this deliverable (section 2-5), which differ in scale and are focused on the wastewater flows, their reuse and the recovery of nutrients and energy. The case studies delve into city wide scaling of the project as well as micro level projects which were missing in the previous deliverable.

Table 1 Table of previously listed case studies

Case study No.	Project	Description
1	Wider Uptake	Solutions based on a circular economy to recover resources from the water cycle. Focus on the project in Prague, Czech Republic.
2	Cooperative Equilibre'	Cooperative housing projects in Switzerland that have retrofitted the apartment buildings for the source separation and reuse of human faeces as fertilisers for local reuse.
3	Blue factory	In Fribourg, Switzerland, an institutional building that has been designed to separate the waste and grey water at source and treat them in the same building for reuse, hence completing the cycle.
4	EcoSansRes	Ecological Sanitation Research (EcoSanRes) is an international programme related to ecological sanitation. The project based in Sweden demonstrates the collaboration between the municipality, residents, experts and the farmers to reuse urine as fertiliser.
5	Next Gen Circular Water Solutions	In the WWTP Steinhof in Braunschweig, Germany, NextGen aims to optimise the biogas production, and the struvite production process, including the increase of the grain size and a raised P recovery rate. Furthermore, the production process of an ammonium sulphate solution shall be optimised, aiming at a high N recovery rate.

Case study No.	Project	Description
6	La Fumainerie	Bordeaux (France) The Bordeaux-based association installed urine-diverting dry toilets (UDDT) and separately collected urine and faeces for valorisation by project partner companies.
7	Superlocal	Located in Kerkrade (the Netherlands) Superlocal (Super Circular Estate) is a development area with new homes built with reused materials, along with the development of a closed water cycle for 130 households.
8	ULTIMATE	ULTIMATE: indUstry water-utiLiTy symbiosis for a sMarter wATER society is a Horizon2020 project with 9 case studies. Most relevant are the case studies in Karmiel/ Shafdan (Israel) connecting the Karmiel municipal wastewater plant with Israel's largest municipal WWTP Shafdan (Tel Aviv), and the case study Kalundborg (Denmark) where a cooperation between an industrial and a municipal wastewater treatment plant is established.

2. H+ Project, Helsingborg, Sweden

2.1 General description and project overview table

The H+ Project in Oceanhamnen, Helsingborg, Sweden, is an ambitious urban renewal and waterfront redevelopment initiative designed to integrate advanced circular water and nutrient recovery systems into a newly built district. The project is part of Helsingborg's broader goal to become one of Europe's most sustainable cities, with a strong focus on resource efficiency, renewable energy, and nutrient recycling (Run4Life, 2022).

The residential area will eventually house around 1,500 inhabitants in a mix of apartments and other housing units. The innovative wastewater system, developed and operated by NSVA (the regional water and wastewater utility), is designed to separate and recover valuable resources from household wastewater streams. NSVA also plays a central role in educating future residents on how the system works, why separation is important, and how their participation contributes to environmental sustainability.

In addition to technical innovation, Reco Lab which is a test and demonstration facility linked to the project, along with the municipality of Helsingborg, place strong emphasis on public engagement and capacity building. This includes workshops, guided tours, and educational programs to ensure residents understand the technology and feel positive about using products derived from their waste. Stakeholder collaboration also extends to

monitoring public acceptance of recovered resources, which is essential for scaling such solutions citywide (Skambraks et al., 2017).

Figure 1 Analysis table for H+ Project in Helsingborg, Sweden

Funded by the European Union

H + Project (Helsingborg, Sweden)

The Goal	Integration of new infrastructures in a city renewal project for efficient source separation and reuse of waste and production of fertilisers		
Steps	Collection	Logistics and treatment	Fertiliser use
Description	1500 IE which is about 343 households, 3 office buildings and 1 communal building	A separate sewage system for the separation waste water with three different of sewage lines	Tailor made fertiliser products with the recovered struvite and ammonium sulphate
Categories/ sectors of policy making	<p>Differnt pipes for different waste water</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •A vacuum pipe for toilet which uses only around 1l of water per flush, a pipe for bathing and dishwashing and one for food waste with grinders. 	<p>Separate treatments for the three types of wastewater</p> <p>•Blackwater pipes The concentrated black water are transported to the treatment plant with a separate pipe to recover nutrient rich products useful for fertilisers.</p> <p>Food waste pipes •A dedicated pipe with organic food scraps are directed to the anaerobic digestors to produce biogas as a local fuel.</p> <p>Grey waste pipes •The pipe collecting wastewater from showers, bathroom sinks undergoes purification and reused for non potable purposes</p>	<p>Diverse fertilisers from different wastes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The products are mixed in different ratios with hygienised sludge from either the kitchen waste digester or the black water digester Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium (NPK) pellets, according to the requirements.
	<p>Mobilise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Strong city branding ("smart & sustainable Helsingborg") mobilised residents & businesses. <p>Educate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Household training & education on source separation; public demonstration sites 	<p>Manage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The local treatment system is located at the existing Helsingborg sewage treatment plant and managed by project partner NSVA •For regular service and maintenance, plumbing companies are hired. <p>Incentivise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •National innovation & EU funding. •Energy recovery reduces household costs. 	<p>Educate and Mobilise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The RecoLab which fosters research and development and an educational showroom are implemented together with the treatment plant. •Besides technological aspects, communication with end users and acceptance of the concept and products is also done <p>Regulate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Sweden's environmental goals, EU Wastewater Directive, and municipal innovation strategies
Policy Support	Local -> Cooperation between municipality, sewage treatment treatment plant and project developers enhanced by strong city branding		

2.2 Collection

The prime strategy of this district is to allocate three different pipe systems to collect the waste flows separately at the source itself. The black water, food waste and grey water are conveyed through these different pipes and are led to the respective treatment facilities.

By keeping these waste and wastewater streams separate, the system has an improved efficiency of treatment, increased recovery of high quality by products, and reduction of the overall environmental footprint.

2.3 Logistics and treatment

The district's three-pipe system ensures that wastewater is collected separately according to its source and composition:

a. *Blackwater pipe*

Connected to vacuum toilets that use only about 1 litre of water per flush, resulting in a concentrated stream of blackwater rich in nutrients. This water contains high levels of nitrogen and phosphorus, which are recovered at the treatment plant in the form of struvite and ammonium phosphate, both valuable as agricultural fertilisers.

b. *Food waste pipe*

Kitchen sinks are fitted with food grinders, sending organic food scraps through a dedicated pipe to anaerobic digesters. The digesters convert the waste into biogas, which is then used locally for applications such as district heating, electricity generation, or street lighting.

c. *Greywater pipe*

Collects relatively clean wastewater from showers, bathtubs, and bathroom sinks. This water undergoes purification and can be reused for non-potable purposes, such as irrigation or flushing, thereby reducing freshwater demand.

2.4 Fertiliser usage

Tailor made fertilisers from different wastes flows are produced in this system. The products are mixed in different ratios with the treated sludge from either the kitchen waste digester or the black water digester. The fertilisers such as NPK (Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium) pellets are also produced according to the requirements of the farmers.

2.5 Policy Support

This project stands as a leading city-scale example of how urban development can integrate circular economy principles into everyday infrastructure by closing loops for

water, energy, and nutrients while building a more sustainable and resilient city. It is embedded in Sweden's environmental goals, EU Wastewater Directive, and municipal innovation strategies which can be a steppingstone to implement such strategies in regional and municipal level (Skambraks et al., 2017).

3. Hamburg Water Cycle

3.1 General description and project overview table

The Jenfelder Au in Hamburg, Germany, is a flagship urban redevelopment project that integrates water, energy, and nutrient cycles at the district scale. Built on a former military barracks site in the Wandsbek district, the development houses around 770 residential units and community facilities, serving approximately 2,000 residents. At its core, the project implements the Hamburg Water Cycle (HWC), a decentralized wastewater management concept that separates waste streams and harnesses them for energy and resource recovery. The description of the project is based on the condensed report by Schelbert et.al (2023).

Figure 2 Analysis Table for Hamburg Water Cycle in Hamburg, Germany

Hamburg Water Cycle (Jenfelder Au, Hamburg, Germany)

The Goal	A decentralised wastewater management concept that separates waste and water streams and harnesses them for energy and resource recovery.		
Steps	Collection	Logistics and treatment	Fertiliser use
Description	Collection of wastewater from around 770 residential units and community facilities, serving around 2,000 residents	A separate collection of waste water, grey water, black water and rain water that undergo respective treatments	Bio gas produced and used for local energy production
Categories/ sectors of policy making	<p>Waste water separation at source</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Source separation of wastewater into black water , grey water and rainwater. •Vacuum toilets installed in all homes to minimize water use and to efficiently transport concentrated black water through a dedicated pipe system. •Grey water and rainwater are collected separately and directed to specific treatment units. 	<p>Separate treatment of waste waters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The concentrated black water is digested in anaerobic digesters to produce biogas which feeds into combined heat and power. •Grey water is treated in a local treatment plant and discharged into nearby water bodies or infiltrated into the soil which relieves the municipal system. •Rainwater management is integrated with green-blue infrastructure: open channels, retention basins, and green spaces slow runoff and enhance infiltration. 	<p>From wastewater disposal problem to resource</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •HWC system uses wastewater into producing renewable biogas, and contributes to the local energy balance and climate goals. • The produced biogas help to generate electricity and heat for the neighbourhood covering about 40% of the district's heat demand. •The reuse of treated water is not the main focus, but is considered to be of higher quality and conveyed towards the water body or infiltrated in soil.
	<p>Educate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Mobilisation through city leadership, housing developers, and trust-building by municipal utility. <p>Regulate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Amendment to the Hamburg Wastewater Act in 2018 to include 'partial wastewater flows' 	<p>Manage and Educate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information campaigns on vacuum toilets, separation, and local energy cycles; technical support for households. • Hamburg Wasser (municipal utility) leads integration with housing developers & planners. 	<p>Incentivise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compared to conventional sewer-based systems, the HWC at Jenfelder Au reduces CO₂ emissions with funding provided by Hamburg Senate and EU's Horizon 2020 program • Residents benefit from renewable energy & localised treatment.
Policy support	Local -> The project is supported by Hamburg's Climate Action Plan, German Renewable Energy Act (EEG), and EU directives on wastewater/resource recovery and is aligned with Germany's energy transition strategies. Replication in regional and local scale can be done through the learnings of this example		

3.2 Collection

The system is based on the source separation of wastewater into black water (toilet waste), grey water (from showers, sinks, washing), and rainwater. Vacuum toilets are installed in all homes to minimize water use and to efficiently transport concentrated black water through a dedicated pipe system. Grey water and rainwater are collected separately and directed to specific treatment units.

3.3 Logistics and treatment

- **Blackwater**
The concentrated black water is digested in anaerobic digesters to produce biogas. This biogas feeds into combined heat and power (CHP) units that generate electricity and heat for the neighbourhood. The process provides about 40% of the Jenfelder Au project area's heat demand, significantly reducing reliance on fossil fuels. Nutrients in the sludge can also be recovered for fertiliser use.
- **Grey water**
Grey water is treated in a local treatment plant and then discharged into nearby water bodies or infiltrated into the soil. While the Jenfelder Au focuses less on direct reuse of grey water compared to other projects, the treatment ensures high environmental quality standards and relieves the municipal system.
- **Rainwater**
Rainwater management is integrated with green-blue infrastructure: open channels, retention basins, and green spaces slow runoff, enhance infiltration, and create recreational and ecological value. These visible water elements also raise public awareness of sustainable water management.

3.4 Resources usage

The HWC system turns wastewater from a disposal problem into a resource. By producing renewable biogas, it contributes to the local energy balance and climate goals. Compared to conventional sewer-based systems, the Jenfelder Au reduces CO₂ emissions and supports Germany's energy transition strategies (Schelbert et.al, 2023)

3.5 Policy support

The project is supported by Hamburg's Climate Action Plan, the German Renewable Energy Act (EEG), and EU directives on wastewater/resource recovery. The relentless support of people in key positions helped to politically legitimize decentralized sanitation and water management systems and identify potential collaboration and synergies (Skambraks et al., 2017; Schelbert et. al, 2023). This initiative is also aligned with Germany's Replication of core features in regional and local scale can be initiated with this example.

4. De Nieuwe Dokken

4.1 General description and project overview table

The Nieuwe Dokken project is a large-scale real estate urban development initiative located in an old industrial port area situated along Schipperskaai, Ghent. It is widely recognised as a pioneering example of how circular economy principles can be embedded into city districts, combining sustainable housing with closed loop systems for water, energy and nutrients (De Nieuwe Dokken, 2025; RENergetic, 2024).

The project was led by Schipperskai Development in collaboration with the urban development agency, Sogent. It integrates advanced decentralised wastewater management technologies by separating the household waste streams at the source, enabling the recovery of valuable by products like fertilisers and biogas, while reducing freshwater demand and emissions (ibid). In this sense, it is closely aligned with Helsingborg's H+ project in Sweden, but it further distinguishes itself through its strong cooperative governance, business model and policy framework.

The project was publicised as “Creation of a new city district next to Gent (Oude Dokken – Kaaimuur Achterdok Oost)” with the total investment of EUR 2,480,089, with the EU’s European Regional Development Fund contributing EUR 959,504 through the “Flanders” Operational Programme for the 2007-2013 programming period (European Commission, 2018).

Figure 3 Analysis Table for De Nieuwe Dokken in Ghent, Belgium

De Nieuwe Dokken (Ghent, Belgium)

The Goal	Real estate development in an old industrial port area in Ghent, Belgium with decentralised waste water management with other sustainable technologies		
Steps	Collection	Logistics and treatment	Fertiliser use
Description	Collection of different waste streams from about 400 apartments and mixed use buildings	Different collection pipes for different waste streams	Purified wastewater for local use and production of heat and struvite
Categories/ sectors of policy making	Different pipes for different waste water <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •A vacuum pipe for blackwater and food waste while greywater is collected by a separate insulated pressure sewer 	High tech and integrated wastewater treatment systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The water treatment system combined technologies like vacuum sewer systems, digestion of black water, struvite recovery and recovery of waste heat from the effluents of WWTPs with a heat pump and an aerobic membrane bioreactor 	Heat and energy recovery from biogas and production of struvite <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Estimated yearly reuse of over 30,000m³ of freshwater, recovery of over 750 MWh of waste heat from biogas covering about 1/3rd of the districts heat demand. It also covers the production of 1500 kg of struvite
	Educate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Awareness on the sustainable values of the project by calling for participation in meetings, information sessions etc. Mobilise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cooperative model fosters resident participation in decision-making and system operations. 	Manage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Cooperative DuCoop manages water-energy loops; real estate developer Schipperskaai Development and city agency Sogent oversee implementation. •Generation of income from heat recovery from wastewater Incentivise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixed housing (budget, social, high-end) making the technologies accesible to all. Regulate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ghent's climate & circular economy strategies; backed by EU innovation programs promoting decentralised systems. 	Incentivise <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Economic: reduced energy bills, reclaimed fertilizers, cheaper local heat. •Environmental: closed-loop water & nutrient recovery.
Policy Support	Local -> Well informed locals who benefit from production of local heat and energy production Regional -> Cooperative models as an inspiration for sustainable nutrient recovery and energy production		

4.2 Collection

The collection consists of different pipes for different waste streams accumulated from about 400 residential units as well as mixed used buildings like schools, sports halls, day care etc. with a people equivalent of around 1200. The properties are categorised into budget, social and high-end housing. Like in the previous case study, the different pipes carry either black water, grey water, or food waste, and are conveyed to their respective treatment plants (De Nieuwe Dokken, 2025).

4.3 Logistics and treatment

The contents of the different pipe are directed into diverse treatment plants described below according to RENergetic (2024)

- a. Blackwater
About 1500 kgs of struvite is produced from the treatment of black water which is used to produce fertilisers for agriculture
- b. Grey water
The grey water from the household is conveyed towards the water treatment plants to recover the water. It is estimated that over 30,000 m³ of freshwater is reclaimed and reused within the vicinity. The processed water is directed towards the neighbouring industry and the residual effluent heat is used up for the district heating network.
- c. Food waste
The food waste is transferred to the plant with digestors which produce energy in the form of biogas. The power plant manages solar PV, battery storage, EV charging as well as heat pumps. About 750 MWh of waste heat is recovered which is about one third of the districts heat demand which has optimised the local energy use.

4.4 Fertiliser usage

The struvite is the main ingredient that is reclaimed to produce fertilisers to use for agriculture (ibid).

4.5 Policy support

This project is also quintessential in terms of district scale urban development integrated with the circular economy principles for water, energy and nutrients and put emphasis on citizen participation. The main takeaway of this project is the establishment of the cooperative DuCoop, driven by the active involvement of the residents to create a sustainable source of water and energy (Skambraks et al., 2017). Besides the technological aspects, the project also exemplifies the integration of blue green corridors, parks, and green spaces to foster biodiversity and communal interaction. It is supported by Ghent's climate & circular economy strategies; backed by EU innovation programs promoting decentralised systems (European Commission, 2018).

5. Saint-Germé public primary school, France

5.1 General description and project overview table

The primary school was constructed on the outskirts of the village of Saint-Germé in 2012 with an aim to be an exemplary building to demonstrate ecological sanitation practises. It is in fact the first public school in France to be fully equipped with dry toilets. The project was initiated by the Armagnac-Adour community of communes. The project was developed by an architectural firm named Airoidi and Brun while the implementation of the sanitation systems was entrusted to the Pierre et Terre association. The details of the project were translated from the report by OCAPI and L'Institut Paris Region published in 2012 (OCAPI & L'Institut Paris Region, 2012).

Figure 4 Analysis Table for Saint Germé primary school in France

Saint Germe´ Public Primary School, France

The Goal	Demonstration of decentralised sanitation system to young pupils in an institutional building i.e a public primary school in rural France		
Steps	Collection	Logistics and treatment	Fertiliser use
Description	Collection of faeces and urine is done through dry toilets used by around 60 children and 10 adults	Roughly 200 litres of mineralised compost per unit are accumulated, with a theoretical emptying frequency of once every 7 years (appx 400,000 uses)	Although, no explicit nutrient recovery done, pedagogical demonstration of compost extraction in classroom projects is done
Categories/ sectors of policy making	<p>Meticulous design of the infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Special attention given to the design of lighting, ensuring waste stacks are not directly illuminated to prevent discomfort and reduce nuisances linked to insect attraction 	<p>Small scale and low tech collection and treatment of urine and faeces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •The discharges are conveyed to the composters with capacity of 650L fitted with air extractors and filters and facilitated by gravity separation of faeces and urine and directed to planted filters. •Periodic addition of carbon-rich material like wood chips. •Maintenance of the composters is minimal • Occasional treatment with charcoal based insect repellent if midges appear 	<p>Pedagogical potential of such systems with occasional recovery of compost</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •A teacher-led project used compost to amend soil and to grow seedlings, later sold to benefit the school
	<p>Incentivise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Ecological sanitation showcases for rural schools <p>Regulate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •France's rural ecological sanitation programs 	<p>Manage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong role of local association and low maintenance cost and effort • Armagnac-Adour community of communes, designed by an architectural firm, sanitation managed by Pierre et Terre association <p>Incentivise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Low water use and low cost infrastructure •Educational incentive for children 	<p>Educate and Mobilise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily exposure for over 70 users including children and staff • Teacher driven initiatives for educational projects with compost samples and on site use. For eg. using compost in school garden
Policy support	Local -> Beyond resource recovery, these sites create opportunities for education, awareness and community discourse, helping future generation to normalise and prioritise alternative sanitation practises, starting from an early age.		

5.2 Collection

The facility serves around 60 children and 10 adults on a daily basis. Sanitation relies entirely on dry toilets, which collect faeces and urine without the use of water. The school is equipped with:

- 6 children’s dry toilets (4 for girls, 2 for boys)
- 1 mixed adult dry toilet
- 5 dry male urinals for children
- 3 hand basins

Special attention was given to the design of lighting, ensuring waste stacks are not directly illuminated to prevent discomfort and reduce nuisances linked to insect attraction.

5.3 Logistics and treatment

Each toilet discharges into a sealed 650 L composter located in the basement technical room, directly below the toilet block. The composters are fitted with:

- Air extractors to prevent odours.
- Leachate evacuation systems (pumps and pipes) that transfer liquid residues to planted filters.

The composting process is facilitated by:

- Gravity separation of faeces and urine
- Periodic addition of carbon-rich material (e.g., wood chips)
- Occasional manual breaking of collected compost to maintain aeration.

Urine from the dry urinals, as well as greywater from hand basins, flows by gravity to planted filters. These filters consist of:

- Two vertical beds (operating alternately).
- A horizontal bed in three levels.
- A final infiltration beds.

The planted filters are not accessible to the public and follow standard maintenance protocols.

Maintenance of the composters is minimal:

- Carried out once per school holiday by a volunteer teacher.
- Conducted externally through inspection hatches.
- Occasional treatment with charcoal-based insect repellent if midges appear.

The composters accumulate roughly 200 litres of mineralized compost per unit, with a theoretical emptying frequency of once every 7 years (approximately 400,000 uses). In practice, no full emptying has occurred in the first 10 years of operation.

5.4 Fertiliser usage

Although nutrient recovery was not a central goal, occasional compost extraction has been carried out for educational purposes. For example, a teacher-led project used compost to amend soil in a conservation orchard and to grow seedlings, which were later sold to benefit the school. This illustrates the pedagogical potential of such systems, even when large-scale resource recovery is not prioritised.

5.5 Policy support

The Saint-Germé school demonstrates that public buildings such as schools, universities, and administrative facilities can effectively serve as testbeds for decentralized ecological sanitation systems. Beyond resource recovery, these sites create opportunities for education, awareness, and community discourse, helping future generations to normalise alternative sanitation practices and ecological responsibility.

6. Taxonomy of governance frameworks

To analyse the case studies more closely, their policy instruments were extracted and fit into the framework with the five categories of urban policy instruments framework. The five categories according to Russell et al. (2020) titled, The Urban Policy Instrument Framework, 2020, are

- Mobilise
The theme 'sets the direction of and builds momentum towards long term change, while also determining how this direction is determined and governed.'
- Educate
The theme 'increase the overall levels of awareness and builds necessary skills and knowledge around the circular economy to foster long term change.'
- Manage
The theme 'influences the use and function of physical and material elements within the urban environment.'
- Incentivise
The theme 'sends market signals and support to businesses, citizens and governments to promote certain activities.'
- Regulate
The theme 'changes the rules of the systems to achieve compliance through enforcement.'

These mechanisms are identified from each of the case studies and are tabulated as follows:

Table 2 Taxonomy table for the case studies

Project	Mobilise	Educate	Manage	Incentivise	Regulate
H+ Helsingborg Project (Sweden)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong city branding (“smart & sustainable Helsingborg”) mobilised residents & businesses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Household training & education on source separation; public demonstration sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Managed by NSVA (regional water utility) with Helsingborg municipality; partnerships with private sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National innovation & EU funding. Energy recovery reduces household costs. Strong sustainability branding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sweden’s environmental goals, EU Wastewater Directive, and municipal innovation strategies
Nieuwe Dokken (Belgium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperative model fosters resident participation in decision-making and system operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resident awareness campaigns on vacuum toilets, waste separation, and cooperative benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperative DuCoop manages water-energy loops; real estate developer Schipperskaai and Development city agency Sogent oversees implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic: reduced energy bills, reclaimed fertilisers, cheaper local heat. • Environmental: closed-loop water & nutrient recovery. • Social: mixed housing (budget, social, high-end). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ghent’s climate & circular economy strategies; backed by EU innovation programs promoting decentralised systems.
Jenfelder Au (Germany)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilisation through city leadership, housing developers, and trust-building by municipal utility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information campaigns on vacuum toilets, separation, and local energy cycles; technical support for households. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hamburg Wasser (municipal utility) leads integration with housing developers & planners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of CO₂ & reliance on fossil fuels. Residents benefit from renewable energy & localised treatment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hamburg’s Climate Action Plan, German Renewable Energy Act (EEG), and EU directives on wastewater/resource recovery.
Saint-Germe Primary School (France)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher-driven initiatives (e.g. using compost in school gardens); strong role of local associations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily exposure for ~70 users (children + staff); educational projects with compost samples & orchards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiated by Armagnac-Adour community of communes; design by an architectural firm, sanitation managed by Pierre et Terre association. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecological sanitation showcases for rural schools. • Low water use & low-cost infrastructure. Educational incentive for children. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • France’s rural ecological sanitation programs

Table 4 Taxonomy table for the case studies listed in D4.1

Project	Mobilise	Educate	Manage	Incentivise	Regulate
Wider Uptake, (Czech Republic)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prague's road map to carbon neutrality by 2035 Technical support from the Czech Technical University, University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communities of Practice (CoP) approach with an emphasis on reuse of wastewater Information sharing through the various media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration among Prague city council, private utility companies, operators of the zoo and parks. Continuous monitoring of impact of fertilisers via cameras & software and collecting evidence to influence change in local regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incentives for wastewater treatment and reuse from the local government and the EU. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Czech Republic has opted against following non-binding EU minimum standards on water reuse for irrigation
NextGen Circular Water Solutions, (Germany)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association with farmers as well as the city of Braunschweig, practical partners and legislative representatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and development for implementation of new technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New infrastructure was built at the WWTP to support and enhance the processes Partnership between farmers and the city of Braunschweig 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct financial support through funding from the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amending and correcting Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 authorizing certain products and substances for use in organic production and updated the Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/12.
Superlocal (Netherlands)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Part of research projects and programs- Urban Innovative Action and Life Climate Action 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Departmental collaboration and engagement The master plan in Kerkrade included aspects like the reuse of building material and a closed water cycle. 	N/A	N/A
Ultimate (Israel/Denmark)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of technologies supporting European Green Deal and its Action Plan for CE. 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private-public partnership with cooperation between a municipal WWTP and an industrial WWTP to reach synergies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private and public investments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The EU Directive 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources. Technologies in the frame of

Project	Mobilise	Educate	Manage	Incentivise	Regulate
					Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse •Laying down rules on making EU fertilisers products available in the market
Cooperative Equilibre, Switzerland	•Extensive research and experimentation, coupled with the mobilization of specialized knowledge among the stakeholders	• Individuals at the administrative level were well-versed in wastewater treatment processes and technologies.	• Adaptation to local configuration and continued research and development. • Maintenance carried out by the families themselves after capacity building. •Further aid by the Aneco association • Regular feedback mechanisms	•Initial costs covered by stakeholders, supported by the residents • Water connection and treatment taxes were granted to some buildings. • Provision of subsidies, which helped reduce the investment costs associated with the system.	• Well developed and accepted urine treatment to produce "Aurin", a commercially sold and used fertiliser
Lu Fumainerie (France)	N/A	•Research and development through OCAPI research program raised the question of missing concepts for circular treatment of human excreta	•The project used existing infrastructure necessary to manage a faster transition to a circular system, while setting up new infrastructural approaches to tackle the problem	•The LaboMobile + encouraged the MAMMO collective to form and carry on the project. •Partnership between private actors and public actors	•Monitoring and enforcement through the order of 7 Sept 2009.
EcoSansRes (Sweden)	•Global sustainability and achievement of the Millenium Development Goals	•Outreach efforts encompass promotion, networking, seminars, publication and social media platforms	•Monitoring and evaluation done by the local farmers of contractors regularly	•Lack of financial incentives	• Environmental policy targets 60% P recovery from wastewater; half to be reused on farmland. •1995 sludge law revision allowed use of urine and wastewater in agriculture. • Environmental Code (1999) supports closed

Project	Mobilise	Educate	Manage	Incentivise	Regulate
					nutrient loop sanitation. •Polluters pay principle and promoting concept of 'Best Available Technology'
Blue Factory (Switzerland)	•Multidisciplinary platform bringing together research, education, entrepreneurship and sustainable development initiatives in a public building	•Self driven initiatives in a commercial building for urine collection	•City of Freiburg, the Canton being the equal shareholders with the initiator of the project	• Initiated and funded by BFF SA to develop a former brewery site	N/A

7. Conclusion for parts A and B

This deliverable focused in Part A on a continued study of the Paris-Saint-Vincent-de-Paul project and in Part B on the study of four new case studies which differed in scale and focus.

Learning from the Paris Saint-Vincent-de-Paul case study the following points can be concluded: The interest of “niches” for the experimentation of source separation should be used to initiate similar projects. For the implementation of such projects the public actors play a key role. In order to design and implement an innovative and transversal project there is a need for time and for an integrative approach. The possibility of “reversibility” and the ability to adapt gradually the project are two conditions in favour of the implementation and well-running of comparable experimental projects. Moreover, to transfer the knowledge elsewhere future projects must be adapted to the specificities of territories (and to the involved stakeholders) to be successful. The different stages of a project require the transmission of knowledge and an “onboarding” of new stakeholders at each phase. Lastly, the need for actions to support users in changing their practices has been highlighted.

In Part B the analysis of cases that was started in D4.1 was continued and completed with additional cases. The focus was set on the small-scale institutional projects and the city-wide scale of projects, the aim was to emphasize the operational frameworks and the importance of citizen participation and capacity building. The discourse around decentralised sanitation systems and localised wastewater treatment and reuse is fundamental to its widespread application. The urban policy framework helped to investigate the different policies that enabled the start, implementation, and sustainability of such projects, while benefiting the communities and the environment.

Both, the in-depth analysis of the Paris Saint-Vincent-de-Paul case and the analysis of in total 12 cases (including D4.1 and D4.2 cases) can serve as orientation for stakeholders who aim to initiate comparable processes. The deliverable D4.4 *Governance framework and implementation guidelines* presents a more straightforward way to support such processes. Some of the analysis results produced in the frame of D4.1 and D4.2 were integrated into the deliverable D4.4.

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